

Country Name	Prevalence per 10000 population	Current health expenditure (% of GDP) [12]	Population[11]	Epileptic people [10]
Afghanistan	45.67	11.82	34636207	158200
Albania	73.45	6.67	2876101	21126
Algeria	52.19	6.61	40339329	210520
American Samoa	89.4	No Data	50448	451
Andorra	56.66	7.01	72540	411
Angola	49.36	2.71	29154746	143895
Antigua and Barbuda	79.5	5.12	90564	720
Argentina	40.11	9	43590368	174824
Armenia	65.11	9.95	2865835	18659
Australia	40.48	10.09	24190907	97936
Austria	48.17	10.35	8736668	42084
Azerbaijan	72.29	4.04	9757812	70541
Bahamas. The	63.29	5.59	395976	2506
Bahrain	56.31	4.86	1409661	7938
Bangladesh	51.08	2.86	159784568	816118
Barbados	66.86	6.68	278649	1863
Belarus	43.62	5.91	9469379	41306
Belgium	65.33	10.76	11331422	74029
Belize	60.98	6.06	367313	2240
Benin	88.78	2.47	11260085	99962
Bermuda	41.83	No Data	64554	270
Bhutan	59.63	3.58	749761	4471
Bolivia	57.04	6.83	11263015	64243
Bosnia and Herzegovina	64.27	9.25	3480986	22374
Botswana	91.05	5.77	2352416	21418
Brazil	51.25	9.17	206859578	1060081
Brunei Darussalam	49.06	2.55	425994	2090
Bulgaria	59.64	7.46	7127822	42511
Burkina Faso	62.48	5.95	19275498	120431
Burundi	72.63	7.17	10903327	79189
Cabo Verde	101.56	4.85	558394	5671
Cambodia	62.14	6.12	15624584	97084
Cameroon	96.61	3.59	23711630	229080
Canada	40.92	11.03	36109487	147748
Central African Republic	37.68	5.44	4904177	18481
Chad	72.54	5.05	14592585	105860

Chile	69.08	8.52	18083879	124915
China	28.05	4.98	1387790000	3892677
Colombia	99.43	7.53	47625955	473541
Comoros	79.17	4.65	746232	5908
Costa Rica	85.37	7.32	4945205	42217
Croatia	58.85	6.74	4174349	24565
Cuba	51.13	12.22	11342012	57987
Cyprus	34.2	6.68	1197881	4097
Czech Republic	64.34	7.11	10566332	67984
Democratic Republic of the Congo	43.15	4.37	81430977	351352
Denmark	45.54	10.25	5728010	26083
Djibouti	74.53	2.73	1023261	7626
Dominica	79.91	5.12	70075	560
Dominican Republic	55.31	4.58	10527592	58227
Ecuador	95.26	7.28	16439585	156608
Egypt	51.74	5.36	99784030	516249
El Salvador	82.37	8.71	6250510	51484
Equatorial Guinea	36.71	3.14	1398927	5136
Eritrea	112.84	3.52	3365287	37975
Estonia	54.62	6.7	1315790	7187
Eswatini	No Data	6.82	1142524	No Data
Ethiopia	56.69	3.6	105293228	596895
Fiji	49.98	3.28	918371	4590
Finland	44.96	9.38	5495303	24707
France	79.62	11.49	66724104	531242
Gabon	56.7	3.11	2086206	11829
Gambia. The	59.2	3.2	2317206	13718
Georgia	69.41	8	3727505	25872
Germany	92.49	11.23	82348669	761662
Ghana	81.44	3.39	29554303	240697
Greece	45.74	8.45	10775971	49284
Greenland	62.65	No Data	56186	352
Grenada	62.85	4.44	119966	754
Guam	47.94	No Data	168346	807
Guatemala	76.73	6.07	15827690	121445
Guinea	74.67	5.4	11930985	89091

Guinea-Bissau	65.56	8.33	1834552	12028
Guyana	66.44	4.02	759087	5043
Haiti	52.94	4.81	10713849	56714
Honduras	79.52	7.71	9460798	75230
Hungary	61.59	6.99	9814023	60440
Iceland	46.06	8.1	335439	1545
India	35.61	3.5	1338636340	4766534
Indonesia	45.11	3.02	261850182	1181120
Iran	62.18	7.82	83306231	517959
Iraq	58.13	3.28	38697943	224948
Ireland	49.45	7.45	4755335	23515
Israel	39.78	7.16	8546000	33993
Italy	47.5	8.73	60627498	287959
Ivory Coast	69.41	3.35	24213622	168075
Jamaica	67.83	5.7	2802695	19011
Japan	24.15	10.66	127076000	306896
Jordan	41.07	7.16	9964656	40921
Kazakhstan	68.12	3.42	17794055	121213
Kenya	51.13	4.75	47894670	244896
Kiribati	47.42	8.41	118513	562
Kuwait	50.37	4.73	4048085	20390
Kyrgyzstan	63.75	6.4	6079500	38756
Laos	50.5	2.69	6891000	34802
Latvia	49.58	6.13	1959537	9715
Lebanon	47.74	7.89	6258619	29876
Lesotho	69.17	8.69	2143872	14829
Liberia	87.39	9.86	4706097	41125
Libya	40.06	6.05	6282196	25165
Lithuania	52.36	6.64	2868231	15017
Luxembourg	55.45	5.07	582014	3227
Madagascar	59.2	5.26	25501941	150960
Malawi	66.03	7.73	17405624	114932
Malaysia	59.65	3.7	31526418	188070
Maldives	50.96	10.31	454252	2315
Mali	52.54	3.77	18700106	98257
Malta	43.2	8.97	455356	1967
Marshall Islands	66.63	15.74	48329	322

Mauritania	92.26	3.1	4051890	37382
Mauritius	76.11	5.71	1263473	9616
Mexico	74.81	5.55	121519221	909062
Micronesia. Fed. Sts.	41.39	13.13	109925	455
Moldova	53.94	7.54	2803186	15121
Mongolia	68.72	4.26	3029555	20819
Montenegro	55.78	8.63	622303	3471
Morocco	57.76	5.5	35107264	202772
Morroco	57.76	5.5	35107264	202772
Mozambique	83.67	7.28	27696493	231743
Myanmar	60.4	5.11	51892349	313438
Namibia	87.59	9.32	2323352	20350
Nepal	62.68	5.42	27861186	174642
Netherlands	53.14	10.29	17030314	90495
New Zealand	37.95	9.24	4714100	17892
Nicaragua	76.75	8.05	6389235	49040
Niger	61	4.53	20921743	127616
Nigeria	67.09	3.65	188666931	1265749
North Korea	35.02	No Data	25389611	88927
North Macedonia	56.37	6.38	2072490	11683
Northern Mariana Islands	106.19	No Data	51133	543
Norway	58.58	10.59	5234519	30666
Oman	53.49	4.79	4398070	23524
Pakistan	54.79	2.57	213524840	116982
Panama	72.48	7.35	4026336	29184
Papua New Guinea	34.17	2.33	8899169	30406
Paraguay	67.12	6.68	6266615	42059
Peru	81.65	4.99	31132779	254196
Philippines	54.43	3.95	104875266	570826
Poland	53.74	6.53	37970087	204047
Portugal	41.85	9.39	10325452	43209
Puerto Rico	76.19	No Data	3406672	25955
Qatar	43.3	3.68	2595166	11236
Republic of Congo	51.47	2.79	5186824	26699
Republic of Serbia	91.06	8.46	7058322	64275
Romania	57.52	5	19702267	113336
Russia	37.71	5.29	144342397	544297

Rwanda	73.67	6.96	11930899	87890
Samoa	42.28	5.1	205544	869
San Marino	No Data	8.63	33834	No Data
Sao Tome and Principe	82.29	6.43	204632	1684
Saudi Arabia	39.25	6.43	33416270	131166
Senegal	86.36	4.26	14751356	127400
Seychelles	68.55	4.96	94677	649
Sierra Leone	56.68	16.53	7493913	42479
Singapore	27.15	4.39	5607283	15222
Slovak Republic	71.13	7.11	5430798	38630
Slovenia	62.01	8.46	2065042	12806
Solomon Islands	39.79	4.41	628102	2499
Somalia	42.59	No Data	14292847	60869
South Africa	68.78	8.08	56422274	388082
South Korea	36.81	6.91	51217803	188521
South Sudan	73	8.2	11066105	80778
Spain	40.23	8.95	46484062	187007
Sri Lanka	77.44	3.86	21203000	164196
St. Lucia	72.44	4.91	176413	1278
St. Vincent and the Grenadines	72.1	4.13	105963	764
Sudan	45.03	5.48	39377169	177328
Suriname	63.32	5.99	581453	3682
Sweden	35.97	10.85	9923085	35691
Switzerland	42.24	11.3	8373338	35373
Syria	51.57	3.05	18964252	97795
Taiwan	47.99	No Data	23540000	112971
Tajikistan	72.26	6.96	8725318	63049
Thailand	57.39	3.94	70607037	405229
Timor-East	52.91	6.9	1224562	6479
Togo	80.65	6.6	7661354	61789
Tonga	42.85	4.82	105707	453
Trinidad and Tobago	73.03	6.84	1469330	10731
Tunisia	42.73	6.26	11685667	49929
Turkey	60.89	4.28	81019394	493338
Turkmenistan	64.92	5.74	5868561	38101
Tuvalu	No Data	13.56	10852	No Data
Uganda	98.91	4.96	38748299	383272

Ukraine	40.17	7.55	45004673	180766
United Arab Emirates	58.04	3.47	8994263	52207
United Kingdom	39.88	9.7	65611593	261683
United Republic of Tanzania	78.82	3.96	54401802	428813
United States of America	44.24	16.79	323071755	1429263
Uruguay	55.54	8.68	3413766	18961
Uzbekistan	86.28	4.72	31847900	274793
Vanuatu	40.04	2.93	283218	1134
Venezuela	94.72	3.92	30741464	291195
Vietnam	58.76	4.52	93126529	547206
Yemen	45.32	4.25	29274002	132676
Zambia	82.19	4.48	16767761	137808
Zimbabwe	60.53	7.47	14452704	87483